

Micro/nanoscale spacers for enhanced thermophotovoltaic and thermionic energy conversion: a comprehensive review

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ABSTRACT

Thermionics and thermophotovoltaics are solid-state technologies that convert high-temperature heat into electricity by utilizing fundamental particles—electrons in thermionics and photons in thermophotovoltaics—as energy carriers. Both systems have the potential to achieve high efficiency and power density, contingent on the optimization of radiative/electronic energy fluxes. A critical factor in enhancing energy flux in these devices is the introduction of microscale (thermionics) or nanoscale (thermophotovoltaics) gaps between the hot thermal emitter and the cooler receiver. In thermionic converters, microscale gaps mitigate space charge effects that create energy barriers to electron flow. For thermophotovoltaic systems, nanoscale gaps facilitate photon tunneling, significantly boosting photon flux towards the thermophotovoltaic cell. Forming these small-scale gaps often necessitates intermediate materials or spacers between the emitter and receiver. Over the past few decades, various spacer designs have been proposed and studied, demonstrating their effectiveness in enhancing energy transfer and conversion. However, challenges remain regarding their reliability and scalability. This article provides a comprehensive overview of spacer technologies for thermionics and thermophotovoltaics and summarizes recent advancements, current capabilities, and persistent challenges.

1. Introduction

Thermal to electric energy conversion is the source of most of the world's power. Heat used for energy conversion can be extracted from fossil fuels [1], nuclear reactions [2], as well as renewable sources such as concentrated solar power systems [3]. Another potential source could be heat produced by industrial processes, as two thirds of the primary energy consumption from fossil fuels is lost, mostly as waste heat [4–6]. Additionally, heat storage systems coupled with thermophotovoltaic devices present an alternative to electrochemical batteries [7,8]. Dynamic systems such as steam and gas turbines are currently the most common thermal-to-electric energy converters, but they are cost effective only on a large scale. Solid state devices present a promising modular alternative because their efficiencies do not depend on size, subsequently allowing for the recovery of heat scattered in homes, vehicles, industry, etc. Solid state converters are of special interest as a solution to energy storage because they can be implemented in relatively small systems when compared to dynamic systems. They also offer various advantages compared to traditional converters, such as noiseless operation, easy maintenance, high power density, and scalability [9–11].

Solid state converters are comprised of thermoelectric generators (TEG), thermionic converters (TIC) and thermophotovoltaic converters (TPV). In TEGs, a temperature gradient drives a flow of electrons in a

solid [12], the electron flux is constrained by heat conduction occurring through the medium, which limits the temperature gradient achievable. As a result, the efficiency of TEGs devices is limited to values below 15 % [13]. By contrast, TPVs [14,15] and TICs [16] produce electricity by relying on photons and electrons, respectively, flowing from an emitter to a receiver that are separated by a space. The presence of a gap between the thermal emitter and the receiver enables larger temperature gradients between the hot and cold sides, resulting in higher conversion efficiencies. Currently, the highest experimental conversion efficiency of TPVs is in the range of 25–44 % [17–21], while it is around 15 % for TICs [22,23]. Despite the higher efficiency of TIC and TPV devices, TEGs are the most deployed type of converters [24] because they can operate at temperatures below 800 °C, contrary to TPVs and TICs which need elevated temperatures (>1000 °C) to reach high power densities and conversion efficiencies. So far, to achieve power densities over 1 W·cm⁻², emitter temperatures above 1300 K are needed in TICs [22], and above 1500 K in TPVs [25,26]. However, it is expected that both of these technologies will reach higher efficiencies and power densities by optimizing their design and materials [22,27].

In addition to a heat source, both TPV and TIC devices feature the same basic elements, namely a hot emitter and a cold receiver separated by a vacuum gap. A basic TPV device, depicted in Fig. 1, consists of two main parts: 1) a thermal emitter that is typically at a temperature of 1000–2000 K; and 2) a photovoltaic (PV) cell [14,15]. The external heat

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Fig. 1. Basic components of thermionic and thermophotovoltaic energy converters, inspired by Ref. [31]. Here, the gap between the emitter and receiver is enabled by spacers, represented by cylindrical posts, but other devices can rely on other systems to create the gap.

source heats the emitter, which then emits thermal radiation towards the photovoltaic cell with an appropriate bandgap energy, converting the radiation into electricity. More advanced TPV devices can also include elements to achieve spectral control and optimize radiation exchange such as a selective emitter, filters in the gap and mirrors on the cell. A conventional TIC, illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of similar parts: a cathode that emits electrons once heated to temperatures above 1000 °C [28,29] and a cold anode, usually comprised of a low work function material, that collects the electrons. Fundamentally, the kinetic energy of the cathode's electrons increases as the cathode is heated by an external source until they are able to overcome the cathode's work function and escape from the surface [28,30]. If the cathode and anode are connected by an electrical load, the voltage difference drives a current, and electric power is produced [11].

Over the last few years, researchers have proposed even more advanced hybrid devices that combine various converters. For example, Trucchi et al. [32] proposed a hybrid thermionic-thermoelectric (TIC-TEG) generator for solar energy conversion. In thermionics, researchers have found that introducing a gap between the thermal radiator and the emitter could also lead to improved efficiency [33]. Thermophotovoltaics and thermionics can also be combined to form a hybrid device (TIPV) to further enhance power generation [34–36]. All these approaches, like conventional TPVs and TICs, require the creation of micro- or nano-scale vacuum gaps. Therefore, advanced hybrid converters could also benefit from introducing spacers to separate the hot and cold sides of the device.

2. State of the art of thermionic and thermophotovoltaic devices

2.1. Thermionic converters

Thermionic emission was first noted by Thomas Edison in 1885 when he observed that electrons flowed between two electrodes at different temperatures when separated by a vacuum [37]. Although the first thermionic device was proposed by W. Schlichter in 1915 [38], the development of TICs was minimal until the 1950s when the space race necessitated efficient and compact electricity sources for aerospace missions [5,38]. The first TIC device was achieved by Hatsopoulos and Kaye in 1958 [16]. Due to the limitations of fabrication techniques, research was minimal from the 90s onwards until progress in concentrated solar power and the ability to use sunlight to exploit thermal energy reignited interest in TICs [38]. In practice, however, two main issues hinder the performance of TIC devices: 1) the development of stable materials with a low work function, which are required to fabricate the cathode and anode [39]; and 2) the negative space charge created by electrons that accumulate between the cathode and anode

[11,22,38,39]. This cloud of electrons repels electrons emitted by the cathode away from the anode, preventing electrons from reaching the anode and, consequently, reducing electric power production [11]. Researchers have attempted to mitigate the space charge effect through several methods, including altering the material properties of the cathode surface [11], introducing a plasma [40] or a polarized grid [41] in the gap, or simply reducing the distance [16,42]. Historically, cesium plasma has been used to suppress the space charge effect, but the addition of plasma highly complicates TICs, and the ionization of cesium consumes energy during the conversion process, diminishing the overall system efficiency by as much as 30–50 % [11,22]. Another approach to reduce the space charge effect is adding a gate or grid between the two electrodes to tune the electric field and accelerate the flow of electrons [43,44]. Gates or grids and cesium plasma are advantageous because neither method requires the reduction of the gap distance, which is less constraining than other solutions. However, similar to cesium plasma, power is consumed to maintain the electric field of the gate, which reduces the overall efficiency [22]. The most straightforward way to reduce or nullify the space charge effect is to decrease the vacuum gap separating the cathode and anode. If the distance separating the two electrodes is less than 10 μm, the space charge effect can be effectively avoided [38] because there is neither sufficient space nor time for electrons to collide with each other and form a cloud [11]. Previously, interest in spacer-based TICs was constrained to academia due to the challenges of maintaining close spacing between two surfaces over large areas with extreme temperature differences [37]. Only recently were micron-gap TICs considered feasible and reliable options for energy converters, mostly due to advancements in nanofabrication technologies [22,38]. Plasma-based converters are able to achieve power densities above 10 W.cm⁻² [45], but their efficiencies remain low (<15 %) due to the plasma's energy consumption [11]. Including a gate between the electrodes has so far produced only low power densities (on the order of mW.cm⁻²) [41], mainly due to electron shading by the gate [22]. However, spacer-based solutions (i.e., utilizing small pillars to physically separate the hot and cold sides of a device) have achieved a power density of 1.5 W.cm⁻² [31] and are less complex than plasma- or gate-based solutions, thus representing an interesting alternative to mitigate the space charge effect.

2.2. Thermophotovoltaic generators

Research and development of TPV devices began after that of thermionics. The first TPV device was fabricated by Henry H. Kolm in 1956 and consisted of a silicon solar cell irradiated by a Coleman camping lantern with a gas mantle [5,46,47]. However, Pierre Aigrain is typically credited with the invention of the TPV device [47], and his lecture series proposing direct heat-to-electricity conversion via thermophotovoltaics at MIT from 1960 to 61 was influential in motivating TPV research. Early TPV research focused on the development of low weight and portable electric generators for the military. The energy crisis in the mid-70s motivated research on solar powered applications for TPV, but the lack of high-quality photovoltaic cells stifled interest until the development of GaSb [48] and InGaAs cells in 1990 [49]. This spurred new developments, most notably a thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency of 23.6 % in 2004 [50], which was only recently surpassed [17]. Several full systems were constructed up until the early 2000s, including the first commercial TPV device developed by JX Crystals [51]. In the following years the interest in TPV slowed despite the commencement of research on near-field TPVs (NF-TPV) [52,53]. The current renewed interest in TPV devices can be attributed to the need for energy storage systems, and the development of thin-film InGaAs photovoltaic cells [54], as these cells can realize very high efficiencies at high temperatures [14]. Consequently, current TPV systems require high operating temperatures to be economically viable.

Compared to traditional solar photovoltaics, angular mismatch losses, which arise from the difference of solid angles for absorption and

emission between the emitter and the cell, can be avoided in TPVs because the emitter and the cell are in close proximity to each other. Moreover, spectral energy losses can be limited through photonic engineering [14]. However, their output power densities are still lower than that of thermoelectric devices [55] and are fundamentally limited because radiative heat transfer from the emitter to the photovoltaic cell is constrained by the Blackbody limit [56]. In recent years, research has not only focused on improving the efficiency of photovoltaic cells, but also on methods to overcome the Blackbody limit; this would reduce the cost of electricity per watt, especially at lower emitter temperatures, allowing the use of TPVs in a wider array of applications such as waste heat recovery. Theoretical works have shown that there is an inherent trade-off between maximizing the efficiency and maximizing the power output density [57], and a recent study has highlighted that most works on TPVs were not optimized to maximize power output and focused instead on increasing efficiency [26].

Nevertheless, increasing the power density of TPV devices is crucial to reducing the cost of electricity per watt [58,59]. Current cells have a high cost per unit of device area due to the materials and fabrication; this, in conjunction with low power output densities, leads to a very high cost per output power. By comparison, TEGs are less efficient, but can produce power densities up to $\sim 20 \text{ W.cm}^{-2}$ [55]. As previously indicated, one method of augmenting the power density in TPVs is raising the emitter temperature [14] which makes TPVs competitive only for high temperature applications and not for waste heat recovery. However, other pathways exist, such as light pipes, in which an intermediary material is used between the emitter and the cell [60], and electroluminescent heat pumps, where a diode is used as an emitter [61]. Both approaches are susceptible to optical losses limiting their practical applications. Near-field thermophotovoltaics are another way to enhance the power density of TPV systems. In NF-TPV devices, the vacuum gap between the emitter and receiver is scaled down to the order of the thermal radiation wavelength [5,62]. At such nanoscale distances, evanescent waves—electromagnetic waves generated by total internal reflection and that extend the distance of approximately one wavelength normal to the surface of a heat-emitting body [29,63]—can travel from the emitter to receiver, exciting atoms in the receiver and enabling heat transfer in a process called photon tunneling. If the thermal emission source and photovoltaic cell in a TPV device are separated by distances of the order of nanometers, both propagating and evanescent waves contribute to radiative heat transfer, which vastly enhances the output power density. This effect allows NF-TPV devices to output the same power densities as far-field devices but at much lower emitter temperatures. This is of particular interest in systems featuring recovered waste heat as the heat source since temperatures generated are lower than other sources. The concept of NF-TPVs was first proposed in 2000 [52], and in 2001, DiMatteo et al. [53] observed that the short-circuit current of the PV cell increased when the space between the heat source and the cell was diminished. Since then, several theoretical studies have emerged on the concept of NF-TPVs [64–67], while experimental works have focused on heat transfer measurements between two planar surfaces without a PV cell [68–72]. In 2018, Fiorino et al. [73] developed an NF-TPV device that achieved a 40-fold enhancement in output power density compared to a far-field device by implementing a positioner to create a gap less than 100 nm. Other works also demonstrated that output power density increases for gaps around 100 nm [74–77]. The highest power density reported in a near-field configuration ($0.5\text{--}0.75 \text{ W.cm}^{-2}$) was achieved using a piezoelectric activated tip as an emitter to realize gap distances below 100 nm [76,77].

2.3. State of the art of spacers in TPV and TIC

Although the method of electricity production in TICs differs from that of NF-TPV devices, the performance of both technologies can be improved by shortening the distance between the emitter and the receiver. Several approaches exist to produce a nanometer or

micrometer scale gap between an emitter and receiver: actuator-based [73,78], MEMS based [79]; and spacer-based [47,70,71]. Actuator-based approaches are advantageous in experiments because they rely on positioner stages, enabling the exploration of a large range of gap distances with the same setup, but they are difficult to implement at larger scales. Thus far, MEMS-based designs have been limited to small active areas compared to the volume of the device, which in turn introduces important heat losses [80]. Furthermore, MEMS-based systems consume energy to function and are subject to thermal stress. Spacer-based approaches, where a material is intercalated between the emitter and receiver to create a nanoscale gap, are beneficial because they allow for one-body devices without moving parts and are scalable to larger areas. The fabrication of spacers also rely on microfabrication techniques that are well established in the semiconductor industry, and with advances made in recent years, spacers are becoming more and more feasible [62].

To reduce the space charge effect in thermionics, gaps should be of the order of a few microns, with the ideal distance depending on the temperature of the emitter [29]. For gaps smaller than $1 \mu\text{m}$, the near-field effect becomes prevalent, enhancing the radiative heat transfer between the cathode and the anode. While this phenomenon is desirable for NF-TPVs, in TICs, this radiative heat flux competes with the electron flux and is an important source of losses [29]. For NF-TPV applications, gaps lower than 300 nm should be targeted to take full advantage of the near-field effect [81]. In both applications, the spacers share similar requirements: they should leave large open areas to not obstruct the flux of photons or electrons between emitter and receiver while simultaneously limiting the area for potential conduction, and they should be able to withstand high temperatures without breaking. Furthermore, in the case of TICs, the material of the spacer should have a high electrical resistivity to prevent short-circuiting of the device [22].

This work will first give a summary of existing works using spacers to enable micro- and nanoscale gaps before delving into the challenges spacers present, specifically addressing materials, heat losses and fabrication. For both TIC and NF-TPV, several articles did not focus on constructing a device that produces electricity. Most works targeting NF-TPV applications characterize near-field radiative heat transfer between two surfaces without converting heat into power. Research on TICs results in device fabrication more often than NF-TPVs, but several studies focus only on spacer characterization without thermionic conversion. For clarity in the manuscript, the distinction between articles pertaining to NF-TPVs and TICs has been made according to the authors' intended use, but methodology and findings could potentially be applied interchangeably to both applications.

2.3.1. Spacers used in thermionic devices

The first thermionic converter using spacers was created by Beggs [42]. In their device, three pieces of molybdenum foil placed on unspecified ceramic inserts were used to maintain a gap under $6 \mu\text{m}$ between the anode and cathode. At an emitter temperature of 1423 K, an output power of 1 W.cm^{-2} was achieved with a reported efficiency of 4–5 %. In 1993, a thermionic converter was fabricated by Fitzpatrick et al. [82] using alumina spacers to form a $9.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ gap. Very little information about the spacers was provided but an 11.6 % lead efficiency was reported for a temperature of 1300 K. Experiments were conducted under a cesium pressure of 20 or 132 Pa, with the highest efficiency achieved for the lower cesium pressure. From 1999 to 2001, King et al. [83,84] published a series of works demonstrating a TIC with silicon dioxide spacers sandwiched between a cathode consisting of a sapphire substrate and an anode comprised of a silicon dioxide substrate. A layer of a chromium-tungsten alloy and a BaO/SrO/CaO coating were applied to both electrodes to lower the work function. The center of the silicon dioxide anode was etched to form a gap with a minimum distance of $15 \mu\text{m}$; the spacer was created by the non-etched portion of the anode, which formed posts. The next TIC device featuring spacers would come more than ten years later, with Lee et al. [85] fabricating a micro-TIC,

shown in Fig. 2a), with a suspended emitter separated from the collector by silicon dioxide posts. In this work, the poly-SiC emitter coated with BaO/SrO/CaO/W was supported by suspension legs with a U-shaped cross section to increase out-of-plane rigidity and avoid contact between the cathode and anode during heating. Silicon dioxide posts served as support for the suspended emitter structure. This spacer design provided thermal insulation between the cathode and anode and demonstrated stability for several hours at temperatures ranging from 900 K to 1400 K. In 2014, the same group proposed an improved design, in which the emitter was coated with a thin tungsten layer to improve the adherence of the barium oxide. A 5- μm gap was realized, compared to the 10- μm gap previously reported [86]. Littau et al. [87] achieved a gap of approximately 5 μm using alumina microspheres to maintain the gap between a barium-coated tungsten cathode and a tungsten-coated silicon anode. The stated gap size was approximated as the beads' diameters had a large size dispersion. For example, a device with nominal bead diameters between 5 μm and 7 μm produced a thermionic emission I-V curve that better fit the I-V curve of an 11- μm gap. The beads moved around while operating the device, which could cause issues with reliability, as noted by the authors. In 2014, Belbachir et al. [28] separated a SiC cathode and an anode formed by a thin platinum film by fabricating 56 square, silicon dioxide columns on the anode, achieving a 10- μm gap. This work focused heavily on the thermal characterization of the spacers. Notably, the thermal resistance of the spacers, which is the resistance the spacer offers to the heat flux (measured in $\text{K}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$), was evaluated in Ref. [28]. The thermal resistance is a critical aspect of spacer design, as it can be engineered to limit conduction losses through

the spacer. This property depends on the material of the spacer, but also on the quality of the contact between the spacer and the neighboring surface. This aspect will be further discussed in Section 4.2. Conduction losses through the SiO_2 columns were measured by characterizing the thermal resistance of the vacuum gap using calorimetry in an ambient atmosphere. First, the thermal resistances of the cathode and anode were assessed independently, followed by the thermal resistance of the full stack, which consisted of cathode/spacer/anode. At 100 $^\circ\text{C}$, the thermal resistance of the entire vacuum gap, including contact resistances between the cathode and spacers, and between the spacers and anode, was 2.4 $\text{K}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$. This value was used to approximate the conduction losses through the spacers at 830 $^\circ\text{C}$ and was compared to the conduction losses calculated using Fourier's law and the bulk thermal conductivity of silicon dioxide. For the given experimental conditions, the thermal resistance measurements yielded conduction losses of 193 W, while calculations using the thermal conductivity of silicon dioxide resulted in 380 W of conduction losses. In 2020, Campbell et al. [31] proposed an unattached spacer design made of a corrugated film with a hexagonal honeycomb pattern and a U-shaped cross-section to enhance strength and stiffness. This design was based on a design by Nicaise et al. [30] (discussed in section 2.3.2.). In Ref. [31], alumina, an alumina-hafnia alloy, and alumina-hafnia-zirconia nanolaminate films were investigated as spacer materials, as the thin layers in the nanolaminate films increase phonon scattering. Although the article focused on the thermal characterization of the spacers and spacer materials, a TIC was also developed that achieved a 10 $\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ short-circuit current density for an emitter temperature of 1280 K. In 2021, Bellucci et al. [88] compared the output power densities of a device using zirconia spacers (see Fig. 2b)) to form a 3- μm gap and a device employing actuator stages to form a 125- μm gap. For cathode temperatures below 1350 $^\circ\text{C}$, the spacer-based device demonstrated a higher output power density compared to its actuator-based counterpart. The cylindrical spacers were arranged in a ring pattern on the anode to minimize the contact surface between the emitter and the receiver. In 2018, Trucchi et al. [32] proposed a hybrid thermionic-thermoelectric (TIC-TEG) generator using an alumina ring embedded in the collector to form a 100- μm gap in the thermionic portion of the device. In this hybrid device, concentrated solar radiation heated an absorber, which in turn heated a thermionic emitter. As the electrons produced by thermionic emission were collected by the anode, the heat transferred to the anode was used to heat a thermoelectric generator, producing power. A thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency of 6 % was achieved, although the authors identified several ways to optimize the design.

2.3.2. Characterization of spacers for application in thermionics

A few articles focused solely on the characterization or fabrication of spacers, without heat to power conversion, specifically for thermionics. In 2009, Yao et al. [80] proposed semicircular hollow cylinders formed by SU-8 photoresist to achieve a 10- μm -gap and measured their thermal conductivity at temperatures up to 350 K. Although the spacer design was intended for use in a thermionic micro-battery, the authors noted that the spacer material should be replaced for operating temperatures above 400 $^\circ\text{C}$. In 2016, Belbachir et al. [89] reused the design of their previous experiments, described in section 2.3.1, to further investigate the vacuum gap's thermal resistance, specifically the impact of contact pressure on thermal resistance. The sum of the thermal contact resistances between the spacer and each surface increased as the width of the silicon dioxide spacers decreased. Furthermore, the thermal contact resistances between the spacers and electrodes accounted for roughly 80 % of the total thermal resistance of the vacuum gap; thus, interfacial resistances could be critical in reducing parasitic conduction losses. In 2019, Nicaise et al. [30], fabricated an alumina spacer in the form of a corrugated film with hexagonal unit cells, as depicted in Fig. 2c). This spacer film was advantageous because it was fabricated separately and subsequently transferred to the electrode surface, which drastically enhanced the thermal contact resistance at the interfaces between the

Fig. 2. Illustrations of different spacer designs for TICs: a) SEM image (left) of a micro-TEC, and a cross-sectional diagram (right) of the device, as presented in Ref. [85] b) SEM images of the ZrO_2 spacers used in Ref. [88] c) Corrugated, hexagonal spacer as presented in Ref. [30].

electrodes and spacers compared to spacers that are directly fabricated onto one electrode surface. The thermal resistance of the alumina spacer film was characterized in detail, and a small effective thermal conductivity of $5 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ was achieved for a spacer size of $3 \mu\text{m}$. This work was further built up on in 2020 with a similar design, but small protrusions referred to as “bumps” were placed at the hexagon intersections to augment the interfacial contact resistance and multilayered materials were used as discussed in section 2.3.1. [30]. Although the gap distance ranged from $1.8 \mu\text{m}$ to $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, the authors concluded that this design potentially could be scaled down to 100 nm to create nanogaps useful for NF-TPV applications.

2.3.3. Spacers used in near-field thermophotovoltaic devices

To our knowledge, only five articles have resulted in actual NF-TPV devices featuring spacers. The first spacer-based NF-TPV device was proposed by DiMatteo et al. [53] in 2001. Cylindrical, silicon dioxide spacers were fabricated onto a silicon heating chip, which acted as the emitter, to achieve a $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ gap. A piezoelectric actuator was also employed to induce oscillations of the emitter and the gap and measure its impact on the short-circuit current of the TPV cell. The short-circuit current was shown to increase as gap size decreased, suggesting the impact of the gap size on the number of photons being absorbed in the TPV cell. DiMatteo et al. [90] made further progress in 2004 by achieving a higher emitter temperature, smaller gap distances and a larger emitter area. Also, compressible tubular spacers were placed within pits etched on the emitter, as opposed to the solid cylinders in Ref. [53]. Calculations indicated that the compressible spacers’ hollow nature and increased length created by the pits reduced parasitic heat

conduction by nearly 93 %, from $3.78 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in Ref. [53] to $0.27 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in Ref. [90]. In both articles, the gap distance was determined by measuring the capacitance between the emitter and PV cell, whereas most subsequent works measured the gap by interferometry or simply assumed that the gap was equivalent to the length of the spacers. Spacers were not used in NF-TPV devices for many years until 2019, when Inoue et al. [74] developed a one-chip design integrating the emitter, spacers and receiver into one compact device. This device featured a silicon emitter that was suspended over an intermediate silicon substrate and a thin-film InGaAs cell by a supporting beam. Although the gap was created by the suspension of the emitter above the intermediate substrate, the full intermediate silicon layer was considered the spacer in this design. This layer contained pits with a single supporting pillar that enabled the use of reflection spectra measurements to assess the gap distance. Additionally, the intermediate layer served as a transmission medium towards the PV cell. Although thermal deformation of the emitter was observed, resulting in a larger gap size than intended, a gap distance of 140 nm was still achieved, as well as a large temperature difference ($>700 \text{ K}$) between the emitter and the PV cell. A 10-fold enhancement in the short-circuit current and output power were observed in the near-field device compared to a far-field device with a 1160-nm gap. The same group further improved the design in 2021 by adding supporting beams at all four corners of the emitter [91], as shown in Fig. 3a), instead of a single beam. The emitter thickness was also increased from $2 \mu\text{m}$ [74] to $20 \mu\text{m}$ [91] to augment the density of photonic states inside the emitter. The single-beam device featured in Ref. [74] was not rigid enough to prevent contact between the emitter and intermediate substrate, but the more robust device in Ref. [91]

Fig. 3. Illustrations of the different spacers strategies: a) A one-chip NF-TPV device as presented in Ref. [91]; b) Embedded spacers used by Selvidge et al. in Ref. [92]; c) Polystyrene spheres proposed in Ref. [68]; d) SEM images of the truncated pyramids of various heights that were fabricated in Ref. [69]; e) Device design with different heights posts used in Ref. [71]; f) Drawing of the design in Ref. [93]; g) Spacers embedded in the emitter as presented in Ref. [94] h) Design used in Ref. [95] featuring the graphene-based multilayers.

output a power density of $192 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at an emitter temperature of 1192 K, exhibited a system conversion efficiency of 0.7 %. It should be noted that the active heat transfer areas in Refs. [74,91] were very small (1 mm^2). However, Selvidge et al. [92] recently introduced a self-supported emitter-cell device with an area of 0.28 cm^2 and a 150-nm gap, as shown in Fig. 3b). The spacers in this device were four long, GaAs posts formed through etching of the GaInP/GaAs emitter. The device generated an output power density of $4.4 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at $460 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and demonstrated a short-circuit current that far exceeded the photocurrent limit, confirming super-Planckian behavior.

2.3.4. Characterization of spacers for applications in thermophotovoltaics

Most researchers' efforts involving spacers for NF-TPV applications have focused on plane-to-plane experiments without PV cells, to experimentally demonstrate the near-field effects that enable radiative heat transfer surpassing the Blackbody limit. In 2008, Hu et al. [68] investigated the radiative heat flux between two glass plates with a gap maintained by polystyrene spheres of $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ diameter, as depicted in Fig. 3c). The measurements were conducted at room temperature, and the experimental setup achieved a temperature difference between the emitter and receiver of $83 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This configuration produced a radiative heat flux that exceeded the Blackbody limit by 35 % across the entire range of emitter temperatures ($\sim 310\text{--}340 \text{ K}$). In 2015, Ito et al. [69] investigated the radiative heat transfer between two planar silicon dioxide substrates separated by spacers of the same material in the form of truncated pyramids, as illustrated in Fig. 3d). The spacers were fabricated on both the emitter and receiver surfaces to achieve a 500-nm gap. The thermal resistance of the pyramidal structures was also modeled to approximate conduction losses through the spacers. For all of the spacer lengths investigated ($0.5 \mu\text{m}$, $1 \mu\text{m}$ and $2 \mu\text{m}$), the contact resistance between the spacers and the SiO_2 substrates far outweighed the resistance of the bulk of the spacer, confirming the importance of contact resistance in mitigating conduction losses. In 2017, Ito et al. [96] reduced the gap distance to 370 nm and replaced the receiver with a silicon dioxide substrate coated with vanadium oxide, taking advantage of the metal-insulator transition of tungsten-doped vanadium oxide to modulate the radiative heat flux. In 2016, Watjen et al. [70] measured the radiative heat transfer between two silicon plates with areas of 1 cm^2 separated by a minimal gap of 200 nm, which was created by silicon dioxide columns. The gap distance was determined by infrared reflectance measurements, and the radiative heat transfer was approximated by subtracting the estimated conduction losses through the spacers from the total heat flux, which was measured by calorimetry. During the same year, Bernardi et al. [71] also measured the radiative heat transfer between two silicon plates, but their design included both SU-8 and silicon dioxide posts to form a 150-nm vacuum gap. The silicon dioxide posts had a height of 150 nm; they were located in the center of the device and served as a stopping point for the emitter when pressure was applied, as shown in Fig. 3e). The $3.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -tall SU-8 spacers were placed at the edge of the device and were only used to maintain the emitter suspended in far-field conditions. This design allowed for a tunable gap distance, but it introduced some uncertainties in properly defining the active heat transfer area and by consequence in quantifying properly the heat transfer. For a temperature difference of $\sim 116 \text{ K}$, the maximum radiative heat flux between the two 25-mm^2 silicon plates was 8.4 times larger than the Blackbody limit.

In 2017, Lang et al. [72] used silicon dioxide nanospheres to maintain a 150-nm gap between two glass plates. While the vast majority of researchers measured the steady-state heat transfer across the vacuum gap, the measurements in Ref. [72] represent the transient heat transfer. Despite a very minor temperature difference of 7 K, the observed near-field heat flux was 16 times larger than the Blackbody limit. In 2018, Yang et al. [93] coated two planar silicon substrates with graphene to explore whether graphene enhanced or diminished the radiative heat transfer between the surfaces in a design illustrated in Fig. 3f). In this setup, AZ photoresist was utilized to fabricate posts and achieve a

gap of 430 nm. A larger heat transfer coefficient was observed when both the emitter and receiver were coated in graphene due to plasmonic mode coupling, demonstrating the utility of graphene in enhancing near-field radiative heat transfer. One year later, DeSutter et al. [94] achieved gaps ranging from 110 nm to 900 nm using SU-8 pillars between two *p*-doped silicon plates. The cylindrical pillars were embedded in $4.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -deep pits that were etched into the emitter surface, as depicted in Fig. 3g). These pits allowed for pillars that were much longer than the gap distance, which increased the thermal resistance of the spacers without compromising the near-field enhancement in thermal radiation. For a device with a 110-nm gap, conduction losses declined by a factor of ~ 42 when the $4.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -deep pits were incorporated. Temperature differences up to 100 K between the emitter and receiver were investigated, but the design was inherently limited to lower operating temperatures due to SU-8's instability at temperatures exceeding 450 K. In 2018, the same group compared the radiative heat transfer for two device configurations: the first featured two *p*-doped Si surfaces, and the second was a SiC emitter and a receiver consisting of *p*-doped silicon. In both configurations, the emitter and receiver were separated by a 150-nm gap formed by silicon dioxide nanopillars [97]. The radiative heat transfer coefficient between the SiC-Si pair was slightly larger than its Si-Si counterpart, but the SiC-Si pair exhibited more monochromatic behavior due to surface polariton coupling between the dissimilar materials. In both [94,97], the active heat transfer areas were 25 mm^2 . In 2020, SU-8 was utilized again as a spacer material by Ying et al. [98] to create a 190-nm gap between two *p*-doped silicon surfaces. The authors noted that SU-8 can be used to bond two substrates together to create near-field radiative thermal devices. Polystyrene spheres were employed as spacers by Sabbaghi et al. [99] due to the material's low thermal conductivity. The device was characterized by a 215-nm gap between two doped silicon surfaces coated with aluminum films between 13 nm and 80 nm in thickness. Thinner aluminum coatings corresponded to higher near-field radiative heat fluxes due to non-resonant electromagnetic coupling within the gap, known as the near-field effect, as well as resonant coupling within the thin Al layer, or the thin-film effect. The uncertainty in the vacuum gap distance was higher in this work (around 50 nm) compared to other works. However, unlike other publications using spherical spacers, Sabbaghi et al. [99] implemented the Hertz model to calculate the contact area between the polystyrene spheres and silicon surfaces when estimating conduction losses through the spheres. This work, published in 2020, was the last to use spheres as a spacer.

In 2021, Shi et al. [95] investigated the radiative heat transfer between two surfaces made of five layers of a graphene/SU-8 stack deposited on silicon dioxide. A gap of 55 nm was maintained through SU-8 pillars, as shown in Fig. 3h). The Fermi level of the graphene was tuned by applying a voltage bias, revealing a strong enhancement of the radiative heat flux as a function of increasing Fermi level. The same team followed this work with another set of experiments, but this time, the graphene's Fermi level was tuned even further to couple and decouple surface plasmon polaritons across an 81-nm gap separated by SU-8 pillars. This tuning enabled modulation of the radiative heat transfer between the two surfaces [100]. Furthermore, Shi et al. [100] noted that this method should be feasible for other van der Waals' heterostructures with the appropriate resonance modes. Graphene was also used by Lu et al. [101] in 2022 to demonstrate the enhancement of radiative heat transfer resulting from coupled surface plasmon polaritons and hyperbolic phonon polaritons. In this work, emitters and receivers, composed of intrinsic silicon substrates with identical coatings, were separated by a 400-nm gap created by four cylindrical AZ 5214 spacers. Two coatings were investigated: graphene, a hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) heterostructure, and a graphene/hBN/graphene sandwich. For a temperature difference of 40 K, the graphene/hBN heterostructures produced a radiative heat flux three times larger than the Blackbody limit, while the graphene/hBN/graphene multilayers resulted in a six-fold enhancement. The six-fold increase was attributed to strong coupling of surface

plasmon polaritons and hyperbolic modes. In 2024, the same group similarly explored the impact of different emitters on the radiative heat transfer to a GaAs absorber [102]. Layers of indium tin oxide (ITO) or tungsten/silicon dioxide multilayers were added to a tungsten-coated silicon substrate. Again, the objective was to investigate the impact of surface plasmon polaritons and hyperbolic modes on radiative heat transfer. The gap between the hot and cold surfaces was maintained by five silicon dioxide pillars. When the gap distance was 400 nm, the experiments showed that the emitter featuring tungsten/silicon dioxide multilayers produced a radiative heat flux 4.5 times larger than that of a far-field device (gap distance of 10 μm) due to coupled surface plasmon polaritons at the interfaces between metal and dielectric materials. Furthermore, the boost in radiative heat transfer produced by the multilayers was independent of the vacuum gap size, while the enhancement due to the ITO-coated emitter increased as gap size decreased. Li et al. [103] also investigated the impact of a film on near-field heat transfer by comparing the heat transfer between silicon substrates both with and without a 250-nm-thick silicon dioxide film. The 302-nm gap was maintained by an array of silicon dioxide posts. The addition of the silicon dioxide film increased the near-field radiative heat flux by a factor of ~ 10 when compared to the silicon substrate without a film. The impact of a graphene film on near-field radiative heat transfer was again investigated by Habibzadeh et al. [104]. Two scenarios were considered: 1) radiative heat transfer between two SiC surfaces; and 2) radiative heat transfer between lithium fluoride (LiF) and SiC surfaces. In both scenarios, cylindrical SU-8 posts were implemented to create a 120-nm gap. Unfortunately, the authors noted a large distribution in the spacer length and, consequently, high uncertainty in the actual gap distance. The radiative heat transfer was greater for similar materials than dissimilar materials, but an increase in the radiative heat transfer flux was observed after adding a layer of graphene to the LiF emitter due to the interplay of the surface plasmon polaritons of graphene with the surface phonon polaritons of the dielectric.

3. Discussion

This section provides an overview of the main parameters and experimental conditions of the works discussed in Section 2 to determine general trends in experiments regarding micro- and nano-gaps for NF-TPV and TIC applications. Table 1 summarizes several important parameters for characterizing NF-TPVs and TICs, including the materials of the emitter, receiver and spacer, the shape and distribution of the spacer, the area hosting the spacer, the minimum gap distance, the maximum temperature of the emitter, as well as the difference in temperature between the emitter and the receiver (ΔT) and the vacuum level at which the experiments were performed.

Fig. 4a) summarizes the preceding articles by illustrating the number of articles corresponding to a given spacer material for both TICs and TPVs. Articles that resulted in an energy conversion device and articles focused on characterizing the spacers' thermal properties or radiative heat transfer are separated by color. Most articles focused on heat transfer experiments intended for NF-TPV applications using plane-to-plane geometry. In the case of NF-TPVs, only five devices using spacers were fabricated. For TICs, the situation is reversed, as most of the published works demonstrated actual devices and very few articles focused solely on spacer characterization and fabrication. Fig. 4a) reveals that silicon dioxide is by far the most common spacer material, followed by SU-8 photoresist and alumina. Other organic materials have also been employed, such as AZ photoresist and polystyrene. The prominence of organic materials can be partially explained by their low thermal conductivities, as evident by the values in Table 2; this minimizes thermal conduction losses through spacers. Indeed, SU-8, AZ Photoresist, and Polystyrene all have very low thermal conductivities of 0.2 and 0.18 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. However, organic materials have only been utilized for emitter temperatures below 500 K, as illustrated in Fig. 4b), which depicts how often spacer materials have been used as a function of

maximum emitter temperature. In fact, Fig. 4b) reveals that most experiments on NF-TPVs and TICs were conducted at relatively low temperatures (< 500 K). Such temperatures are conducive to organic materials, as demonstrated by the maximum working temperatures listed in Table 2, but they are far from the target emitter temperatures for NF-TPV and TIC applications. SU-8 is the most common organic material largely because of its ease in patterning through conventional photolithography techniques, but it is not suitable for NF-TPV or TIC devices. Of all the materials listed in Table 2, Fig. 4b) indicates that only ceramics like silicon dioxide, alumina and zirconia have been employed at high temperatures. However, silicon dioxide and alumina have high thermal conductivities of 1.4 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ and 2 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, respectively. Alumina is more thermally conductive than silicon dioxide, which may explain the prevalence of silicon dioxide in NF-TPV and TIC experiments. Silicon dioxide is also advantageous due to its ease of patterning through existing, well-known techniques. Zirconia has a much lower thermal conductivity than alumina or silicon dioxide, and zirconia films have demonstrated higher electrical resistivity than alumina at operating temperatures of 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [88]. However, it has only been employed once as a spacer material in a TIC device, and its performance in NF-TPV devices has never been evaluated. Ceramic materials also have much higher compressive strengths than organic materials, metals or metalloids, as demonstrated by the values in Table 2. A high compressive strength is critical for spacer materials as a force is often applied to the upper emitter surface to correct any bowing in the emitter or receiver, which aids in maintaining a uniform and parallel vacuum gap. However, this applied force can cause deformation or breakage of the spacer [22, 69, 88]. Therefore, the mechanical stability of the spacer materials under applied loads should be analyzed when selecting a spacer material. It should be noted that the thermal conductivity values presented in Table 2 are subject to change with pressure and temperature. Moreover, at nanoscale, some material characteristic such as the presence of defects or the porosity can have an impact on the thermal conductivity [105–107]. These variations in thermal conductivity were not considered in most articles, which has introduced uncertainty in parasitic conduction loss calculations through the spacers.

Fig. 4c) illustrates the highest emitter temperature versus the smallest gap distance achieved in each article. Two regions are clearly visible: vacuum gaps greater than 1000 nm, which are ideal for thermionic applications, and gaps below 1000 nm, which are necessary for NF-TPV devices or near-field radiative heat transfer measurements. In the case of thermionic applications, a wide range of emitter temperatures has been explored, and the highest emitter temperature achieved for a spacer-based TIC thus far has been 1673 K. This TIC employed zirconia columns to maintain a gap of 3 μm [88]. For NF-TPV devices, the minimum gap achieved has been in the range of 120–150 nm [74, 92, 90], while the minimum gap distance for plane-to-plane radiative heat transfer measurements has been 55 nm. This plane-to-plane geometry was conceptualized by Shi et al. [100] using SU-8 spacers. So far, sub-100-nm gaps have only been accomplished using SU-8, but this material restricts operational temperatures below 400 K, as listed in Table 2. Thus, future efforts should focus on creating smaller vacuum gaps with larger temperature gradients using materials that are stable at higher temperatures, unlike SU-8 and other organic photoresists. In the case of NF-TPVs, the highest emitter temperature achieved in a spacer-based device has been 1200 K at a separation gap of 140 nm. This value is close to the emitter temperatures that were reached via positioner-based approaches (1273 K) [77], but it does not come close to emitter temperatures achieved by far-field devices (2673 K) [19]. The minimum gap distance achieved by spacers in plane-plane geometries has been 55–81 nm [95, 100]; this is similar to the minimum gap distance in Fiorino et al. [73], where a positioner-based approach resulted in a 60-nm gap.

At the device level, the area is a parameter of interest because spacers appear to be the most scalable solution compared to MEMS and positioners. Fig. 5 illustrates the area of the surface hosting the spacer, either

Table 1

Key parameters collected to conduct the review. The surface coverage represents the total area of the emitter or receiver surface that is covered by spacers: $SC=N.A_{\text{spacer}}/A_{\text{surface}}$, where N is the number of spacers, A_{spacer} is the contact area of one spacer with the surface onto which it is deposited or fabricated and A_{surface} is the area of the surface on which the spacer is deposited/fabricated. Values denoted with an asterisk were stated explicitly in the corresponding research article, while values without an asterisk were calculated using the information present in the paper. A dash means that the information was not provided in the articles.

Article	Application	Type	Emitter	Receiver	Material of the spacer	Shape of the spacer	Distribution	Area hosting the spacer (cm ²)	Surface coverage	Minimal gap distance (nm)	Maximal T _{emitter} (K)	Maximal ΔT	Pressure (Pa)
Hu, Appl. Phys. Lett., 2008 [68]	TPV	heat transfer	SiO ₂	SiO ₂	Polystyrene	Spheres	Unattached	1,27	4,96E-07	1000	380	83	8,50E-03
Ito, Appl. Phys. Lett., 2015 [69]	TPV	heat transfer	SiO ₂	SiO ₂	SiO ₂	Truncated pyramids	On both sides	1,63	8,00E-06	500	313	20	5,00E-03
Watjen, Appl. Phys. Lett., 2016 [70]	TPV	heat transfer	n-doped Si	n-doped Si	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	–	1,00	3,14E-06	200	337	35	3,00E-04
Bernardi, Nat. Commun., 2016 [71]	TPV	heat transfer	undoped Si	undoped Si	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,25	3,14E-06	150	420	120	1,00E-04
Ito, Nano letters, 2017 [96]	TPV	heat transfer	SiO ₂	SiO ₂ with or without W-doped VO2 film	SiO ₂	Truncated pyramids	Both	1,60	3,06E-05	370	370	45	–
Lang, Sci. Rep., 2017 [72]	TPV	heat transfer	SiO ₂ (fused or BK7)	SiO ₂ (fused or BK7)	SiO ₂	Spheres	Unattached	3,14	7,00E-06	150	300	7	1,00E-03
Yang, Nat. Commun., 2018 [93]	TPV	heat transfer	Graphene on undoped or n-doped Si	Graphene on undoped or n-doped Si	AZ Photoresist	Cylindrical columns	–	4,00	1,96E-05	430	353	50	6,67E-04
DeSutter, Nat. Nanotechnol., 2019 [94]	TPV	heat transfer	p-doped Si	p-doped Si	SU-8	Cylindrical columns	Emitter	0,25	1,00E-04*	110	400	100	5,00E-04
Tang, ACS Photonics, 2020 [97]	TPV	heat transfer	SiC or p-doped Si	p-doped Si	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,25	1,40E-06*	150	380	80	1,00E-04
Ying, ACS Photonics, 2020 [98]	TPV	heat transfer	p-doped Si	p-doped Si	SU-8	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,70	5,25E-06	190	385	85	1,00E-01
Sabbaghi, J. Appl. Phys., 2020 [99]	TPV	heat transfer	Al-coated doped Si	Al-coated doped Si	Polystyrene	Spheres	Unattached	0,25	4,10E-06	215	361	65	1,00E-01
Shi, Adv. Mater., 2021 [95]	TPV	heat transfer	Graphene/SU-8 heterostructures on SiO ₂ /Si	Graphene/SU-8 heterostructures on SiO ₂ /Si	SU-8	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,09	2,79E-04	55	328	25	2,80E-05
Lu, Small, 2022 [101]	TPV	heat transfer	hBN, graphene, graphene/hBN or graphene/hBN/graphene multilayers on undoped Si	hBN, graphene, graphene/hBN or graphene/hBN/graphene multilayers on undoped Si	AZ Photoresist	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	1,00	2,04E-05	400	323	40	1,00E-03
Shi, Nano Lett., 2022 [100]	TPV	heat transfer	Graphene/SU-8 heterostructures on SiO ₂ /Si	Graphene/SU-8 heterostructures on SiO ₂ /Si	SU-8	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,09	2,79E-04	81	308	5	2,80E-05
Li, Appl. Phys. Lett., 2024 [102]	TPV	heat transfer	W-coated Si, ITO/W-coated Si, and SiO ₂ /W multilayers on Si	GaSb	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Emitter	1,00	2,51E-06	200	383	100	1,00E-03
Li, J Quant Spectrosc	TPV	heat transfer	SiO ₂ on undoped Si	SiO ₂ on undoped Si	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Emitter	0,25	4,52E-06	302	337	42	8,00E-04

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Article	Application	Type	Emitter	Receiver	Material of the spacer	Shape of the spacer	Distribution	Area hosting the spacer (cm ²)	Surface coverage	Minimal gap distance (nm)	Maximal T _{emitter} (K)	Maximal ΔT	Pressure (Pa)
Radiat Transfer, 2024 [103]													
Habibzadeh, ACS Photonics, 2024 [104]	TPV	heat transfer	SiC or LiF or LiF with Graphene layer	SiC	SU-8	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	2,25	1,44E-05	120	357	60	1,20E-03
DiMatteo, Appl. Phys. Lett., 2001 [53]	TPV	TPV device	Si	InAs PV cell	SiO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Emitter	0,05	–	1000	408	–	5,33
DiMatteo, AIP Conf. Proc. 738, 2004 [90]	TPV	TPV device	Si	InGaAs PV cell	SiO ₂	Hollow cylinders	Emitter	0,20	–	120	1123	–	–
Inoue, Nano Letters, 2019 [74]	TPV	TPV device	Undoped Si	InGaAs PV cell	Si	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,0025	–	140	1040	>700	1,00E-03
Inoue, ACS Photonics, 2021 [91]	TPV	TPV device	Undoped Si	InGaAs PV cell	Si	–	Receiver	0,01	–	140	1200	900	1,00E-03
Selvidge, Adv. Mat., 2024 [92]	TPV	TPV device	GaAs	InAs PV cell	GaAs	Rectangular posts	Emitter	0,28	8,93E-06	150	733	470	1,00E-03
Yao, Journal of heat transfer, 2009 [80]	TIC	spacer characterization	Si	Au-coated Si	SU-8	Semi-circular hollow columns	Emitter	1,00	5,97E-04	10000	353	30	1
Belbachir, Microsyst. Tech., 2016 [89]	TIC	spacer characterization	SiC	Pt -coated Si	SiO ₂	Truncated pyramids	Receiver	0,84	1,71E-02	10000	373	80	1,01E+05
Nicaise, Microsystems & Nanoeng., 2019 [30]	TIC	spacer characterization	Si	Si	Al ₂ O ₃	U-beam ribs arranged in hexagons	Unattached	0,90	2,17E-03	3000	473	–	4,00E-04
Campbell, J. Microelectro. Sys., 2020 [31]	TIC	spacer characterization	W-coated Si	W-coated Si	Al ₂ O ₃	U-beam ribs arranged in hexagons	Unattached	1,25	7,23E-04	1800	403	40	1,33E-02
	TIC	TIC device	Mo	Mo	Al ₂ O ₃	U-beam ribs arranged in hexagons	Unattached	1,27	–	2300	1280	345	–
	TIC	TIC device	Mo	Mo	Al ₂ O ₃	U-beam ribs arranged in hexagons	Unattached	3,14	–	5900	1330	465	–
Beggs, Adv. Energy Convers., 1963 [42]	TIC	TIC device	SrCaO/Pt-coated W	BaSrO-coated W	Mo and ceramics	Sheets	Unattached	2,8	–	5588	1373	500	–
Fitzpatrick, IECEC-93, 1993 [82]	TIC	TIC device	W-Ta-Re alloy monocrystal	Mo-Nb alloy monocrystal	Al ₂ O ₃	–	Receiver	–	–	9500	1306	509	20

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Article	Application	Type	Emitter	Receiver	Material of the spacer	Shape of the spacer	Distribution	Area hosting the spacer (cm ²)	Surface coverage	Minimal gap distance (nm)	Maximal T _{emitter} (K)	Maximal ΔT	Pressure (Pa)
King, AIP Conference proc., 2001 [84]	TIC	TIC device	BaO/SrO/CaO/W-coated sapphire	BaO/SrO/CaO/W-coated SiO ₂	SiO ₂	unspecified	Receiver	0,84	–	15000	1170	450	vacuum condition but no details provided
Lee, Microsystems Workshop, 2012 [85]	TIC	TIC device	poly-SiC	Si	SiO ₂	Rectangular posts	Receiver	0,0025	–	10000	1650	–	1,33E-04
Littau, Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 2013 [87]	TIC	TIC device	Ba-activated W	W-coated Si	Al ₂ O ₃	Spheres	Unattached	0,32	–	11000	1473	–	6,67E-04
Lee, J. Microelect. Sys., 2014 [86]	TIC	TIC device	BaO/SrO/CaO/W-coated poly-SiC	Si	SiO ₂	Rectangular posts	Receiver	0,0025	–	5000	1400	>1000	1,33E-04
Belbachir, J. Micromech. Microeng., 2014 [28]	TIC	TIC device	SiC	Pt -coated Si	SiO ₂	Truncated pyramids	Receiver	0,84	1,00E-01	10000	1103	462	1,00E-03
Bellucci, Energy Tech., 2021 [88]	TIC	TIC device	W	GaAs	ZrO ₂	Cylindrical columns	Receiver	0,41	3,20E-04*	3000	1673	1120	5,00E-06
Trucchi, Adv. Energy Matls, 2018 [32]	Hybrid TIC-TEG	TIC device	n-doped diamond film on HfC	Mo	Al ₂ O ₃	Ring	Unattached, but embedded in receiver	–	–	100000	1029	521	1,00E-04

Fig. 4. a) Number of articles using different spacer materials for NF-TPVs or TICs according to their application. Plane-plane near-field radiative heat transfer measurements and spacer characterization for TICs are denoted by light red and light blue, respectively. Actual NF-TPV devices are represented by dark red, while TIC devices are represented by dark blue. b) Number of articles that employed various spacer materials as a function of the range of emitter temperatures [K]. c) Maximum temperature of the emitter T_e [K] corresponding to the different gap distances achieved in every article. Triangles represent experiments targeting TICs, with filled markers representing devices and hollow markers being experiments with no energy conversion. Circles represent NF-TPV experiments with a similar distinction between devices and experiments with no energy conversion. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 2
Thermal, electrical and mechanical properties of the most common spacer materials in literature.

Material	Maximum operating temperature [K]	Thermal conductivity [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Electrical resistivity [Ω.cm]	Compressive strength [MPa]
Silicon dioxide	1986 [108]	1.4 [109]	~10 ¹¹ -10 ¹⁶ [110]	1100 [111]
SU-8	450 [112]	0.2 [113]	~10 ¹⁶ [108]	108 [114]
Alumina	2345 [115]	2 [116]	~10 ¹⁴ [108]	2500 [111]
Polystyrene	513 [117]	0.18 [118]	~10 ¹⁸ [108]	0.750 [111]
AZ Photoresist	420 [119]	0.18 [120]		
Silicon	1687 [108]	142 [121]	~10 ⁵ [122]	120 [108]
Zirconia	2988 [108]	0.06 [123]	~10 ¹⁰ [108]	2200 [111]
Molybdenum	2896 [108]	137 [124]	~10 ⁻⁶ [108]	400 [108]
GaAs	1513 [108]	55 [125]	~10 ⁷ [108]	

the receiver or the emitter, depending on the gap distance, for each article referenced in Table 1. Thermionic devices, represented by the points at gap distances above 1000 nm, achieved a bigger area (~2 cm²) than NF-TPV devices. This can be attributed to the fact that fabrication is less challenging at those larger distances and that it is easier to maintain parallel surfaces for larger gap distances, which is not the case for the distances of interest in NF-TPV devices. For TIC the biggest area for a device was 3.14 cm² and was achieved by Campbell et al. [31] for an emitter temperature of 1330 K. The highest emitter temperature for a TIC device was 1673 K, achieved by Bellucci et al. [88], but the area of the device was limited to 0.4 cm². In the case of NF-TPV devices, the biggest area was realized by Selvidge et al. [92] with an area of 0.28 cm², this experiment targeted the relatively low emitter temperature of ~700 K. Nonetheless it represents a considerable improvement compared to other devices, most notably the device by Inoue et al. [91] that achieved the highest emitter temperature (1200 K) but for a device area of 0.01 cm². In addition, the design proposed by Inoue et al. appeared difficult to scale up due to the emitter potentially touching the intermediate spacer. Another notable NF-TPV device is the one fabricated by DiMatteo et al. [90] where a 0.2 cm² emitter area was achieved with the caveat that this area was comprised of an array of four heater chips (of individual area of 0.05 cm²) instead of a single emitter.

Fig. 5. Area of the surface hosting the spacer (in cm^2) plotted against the minimum gap achieved (nm). Color indicates the range of the emitter temperature (in K), filled markers indicate a device (for both technologies) while the shape indicates the material of the spacer. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Regarding experiments with no heat to power conversion, larger areas have been accomplished across the range of gap distances with several experiments achieving areas over 1 cm^2 . However, for gap distances below 100 nm, only small-scale areas (0.09 cm^2) have been reported [95,100], and only for low emitter temperatures, highlighting remaining challenges in scaling up the area for sub-100 nm gaps.

In both technologies, the flux of interest, which is electrons for TICs and photons for NF-TPVs, is not the only heat flux present. Convective heat transfer is suppressed in most cases because experiments are conducted in a vacuum; one exception is thermionics that utilize cesium plasma [82]. However, the introduction of spacers between the emitter and receiver facilitates conductive heat transfer. This conduction competes with the useful energy transfer and represents an unavoidable source of losses for the system because the heat transmitted via conduction does not contribute to the generation of electrical power. All the designs that were reviewed for this article featured different operating temperatures and device areas. Thus, a conduction heat transfer coefficient h_{cond} is utilized for comparison in cases where the authors provided sufficient information to calculate this value; this is only the case for articles focused on NF-TPV applications [68,70–72,94,93,95,97–104]. This coefficient is obtained from the conduction losses Q_{cond} and the temperature gradient between emitter and receiver by the relation: $h_{\text{cond}} = Q_{\text{cond}}/\Delta T$. While the temperature difference between the receiver and emitter ΔT is provided most of the time, only a handful of articles gave a value for Q_{cond} . In most articles, this value was approximated by the authors using Fourier's law (see Equation (2) in Section 4.2.), with the exception of DeSutter et al. [94] and Ito et al. [69,96] both of whom employed finite elements methods (FEM) to estimate the losses. The values of h_{cond} as a function of the gap distance that was achieved in each article are illustrated in Fig. 6a). The temperature gradients in the experiments that are presented in this figure are all relatively low (below 120 K). However, when comparing experiments featuring a similar temperature difference, it appears that h_{cond} tends to increase when the gap distance is decreased. For gaps less than $1 \mu\text{m}$, the lowest value of h_{cond} ($2.3 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) was achieved by DeSutter et al. [94] using embedded posts to achieve a 100-nm gap. For larger-scale gaps, the lowest conductive heat transfer coefficient was $0.24 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ and was attained by Hu et al. [68] using polystyrene spheres to create a $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ gap.

The dashed red lines in Fig. 6a) provide a rough approximation of the

radiative heat transfer coefficients h_{rad} for different emitter temperatures, as calculated by the Stefan-Boltzmann law ($h_{\text{rad}} = \sigma T_e^4/\Delta T$), assuming a Blackbody and a receiver temperature of 300 K. These dashed lines represent an ideal case, since none of the emitters utilized in the literature are close to being a Blackbody. For high emitter temperatures ($T_e > 1200 \text{ K}$), radiative heat transfer could, in theory, exceed conductive heat transfer for most of the experimental setups characterized by such emitter temperatures, except for the experiments in which the gap was less than 100 nm [95,100]. However, the highest emitter temperature for the experiments presented in this figure is around 420 K, which means that not all experiments can be expected to exhibit a heat transfer dominated by radiative exchange. Nevertheless, at lower gap distances, near-field effects enhance the radiative heat transfer by several folds, resulting in a vacuum gap that is still dominated by radiative heat transfer, not parasitic conduction through the spacers.

To mitigate conduction losses through spacers, four distinct strategies have been identified:

- Reducing the surface coverage, which is defined as the fraction of area of the emitter or receiver occupied by spacers (see Table 1). As shown in Fig. 6b), the surface coverage is typically reduced as the gap distance is decreased in an attempt to counterbalance the higher thermal conduction losses. However, upon examining the percentage of total heat transfer comprised by conduction losses, shown in Fig. 6c), this approach does not appear to be successful, as the reduction of surface coverage did not necessarily lead to lower conduction losses.
- Embedding the spacers into the emitting or receiving surface. Another approach applied by a few authors, is to use the length of the spacer to increase the path of heat conduction through the spacers, consequently reducing conductive heat flux. DeSutter et al. [94] fabricated spacers in $4.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -deep pits (as seen in Fig. 3g) to lengthen the conduction pathway while still achieving gap distance nearing 100 nm. Conduction losses were estimated to represent about 4 % of the total heat transfer, which led to a conductive heat transfer coefficient of about $2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. This is the lowest value of h_{cond} achieved in this gap range. DeSutter et al. [94] stated that conduction losses would constitute 45 % of total heat transfer if the same device was fabricated without pits. Selvidge et al. [92] employed a similar approach to form a 120-nm-gap. In this case, conduction losses were estimated to represent 19–26 % of the total heat flux.
- Optimizing the shape and material of the spacer. Some examples include implementing hollow or tubular spacers, as proposed in Refs. [80,90], or fabricating pyramids with a truncated pyramid shape where the top area can be optimized to increase the thermal resistance [69]. Ito et al. [69] designed truncated pyramidal spacers from SiO_2 and were able to realize a 370-nm gap and a conductive heat transfer coefficient of $6 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. This value was the lowest reported for silicon dioxide spacers in this range of gap sizes. However, Fig. 6c) indicates that trapezoidal spacers were only somewhat successful in mitigating conduction losses, as 34 % of the total heat transfer was still attributed to conduction. Employing a material with a low thermal conductivity is another solution; Fig. 6c) reveals that the lowest conduction losses were achieved using SU-8 and polystyrene.
- Using unattached spacers. Designs in which spacers are not attached to either the emitter or receiver can increase thermal interfaces, and this can reduce conduction losses considerably [30,31,72]. This strategy will be discussed in detail in Section 4.2.

Finally, it is worth noting that most articles used Fourier's law to determine the conduction losses with only a few relying on FEM or thermal resistance characterization of the vacuum gap. Utilizing Fourier's law to evaluate conduction losses neglects interfacial contact resistances between the spacers and the hot/cold surfaces, which results in

Fig. 6. a) Conductive heat transfer coefficient versus minimum gap distance. The red dashed lines are the estimated radiative heat transfer coefficients for a far-field Blackbody at various emitter temperatures (420 K being the highest temperature reached in this group of experiments) calculated by Stefan-Boltzmann law. The estimated h_{rad} values corresponding to higher emitter temperatures (800, 1200, 1800 K) are provided as an example. When near-field effects are considered, this approximation should be discarded. The pool of data depicted here is limited due to the lack of data available in published works. b) Surface coverage of the spacer structures, or the ratio of the emitter/receiver area occupied by spacers to the total area, versus the minimum gap achieved. c) Percentage of losses due to conduction through the spacers at various gap sizes. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

overestimated conduction losses. The importance of thermal contact resistance in determining conduction losses will be discussed in detail in Section 4.2.

Based on this discussion a few recommendations can be made in order to implement spacer technology for both NF-TPV and TIC devices. Characterizing the heat flux of spacer-based designs has mostly been limited to temperatures below 600 K and relatively small areas. Efforts should be made to characterize the heat transfer and thermal resistance of spacers covering larger areas and at higher temperatures in order to truly evaluate the impact of conduction losses on the overall system efficiency; this is especially true for NF-TPV devices, as these losses can be larger due to the shorter conduction pathways. Spacers should be designed to mitigate conduction losses, either by increasing the overall thermal resistance by boosting the thermal contact resistance between surfaces or by increasing the length of the spacer structures. Using removable spacers has already proven to be effective in boosting the thermal contact resistance, with corrugated films being a promising approach for thermionics and potentially for thermophotovoltaics if their size could be reduced [30,31]. This approach is seemingly more reliable than using unfixed nano- or micro-spheres, since these spheres have been shown to move during device operation [87]. Increasing the spacers' length can be accomplished by embedding the posts in either the emitting or receiving surface to lengthen the conduction pathway [92,94]. Although this method requires additional fabrication steps that

are less straightforward than constructing spacers directly on one of the surfaces, it is possibly the simplest way to minimize conduction losses while maintaining a robust design. In terms of materials, ceramics such as silicon dioxide, alumina or zirconia appear to be the most accessible materials for use at higher emitter temperatures, especially since experiments utilizing these materials that focus on characterizing heat transfer have been limited to relatively low emitter temperatures that are far from the optimum conditions for TICs and NF-TPVs. Using multilayered materials comprised of several ceramic layers could also be an efficient way of further reducing a spacer's thermal conductivity due to interlayer thermal resistances [31,126]. Combining several approaches to reducing conduction losses could result in even lower conduction losses than any one method alone. For example, using embedded spacers with maximized lengths fabricated from a material with very low thermal conductivity could result in minimal conduction losses.

4. Experimental uncertainties

Several authors discussed the difficulties in determining the contribution of radiative heat transfer in an accurate manner in the case of NF-TPVs. Typically, the total heat flux from the emitter to the receiver is the only heat flux that is measured experimentally; thus, the radiative and conductive heat fluxes must be isolated from the total measured value.

Measuring the vacuum gap distance precisely has also challenged authors, and such gap measurements are crucial in verifying experimental results with theoretical predictions.

4.1. Coexistence of heat transfer mechanisms

The total heat flux is the only heat flux that is measured directly in setups concerned with heat transfer characterization. This total heat flux includes the radiative heat flux and the conductive heat flux through the spacers, the convective heat flux being avoided by operating in vacuum conditions. In the case of radiative heat transfer experiments, the following formula was used to deduce the radiative heat transfer from the total heat transfer measured by calorimetry:

$$Q_{\text{rad}} = Q_{\text{total}} - Q_{\text{cond}} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{rad} is the radiative heat transfer and Q_{total} is the total heat transfer measured in the setup. Therefore, the radiative heat flux values presented in the literature have been deduced using the total measured heat flux and the calculated conductive heat flux. In nearly every article concerned with plane-to-plane heat transfer, Q_{cond} was calculated using Fourier's law or a more sophisticated FEM model. The values obtained from Fourier's law relied on tabulated thermal conductivities, which likely led to an overestimation of the conductive heat transfer. No experimental values for Q_{cond} have been reported in experiments focusing on radiative heat transfer. Therefore, all published values of the radiative heat flux have been approximated. In the near-field regime, the impact of this approximation is probably not significant, considering the radiative heat transfer is greatly enhanced and theoretically far greater than conductive heat transfer. However, an experimental distinction between heat losses and radiative energy transfer has not yet been reported, highlighting a significant gap in current research.

In the case of thermionic devices, the electron flux is produced via the conversion of heat to electrons. Therefore, both radiative and conductive heat fluxes represent parasitic losses for TICs. This explains why the vacuum gap distance cannot be scaled down to nano scale sizes as the radiative heat transfer would be predominant through near field effects. To our knowledge, no experiments have been conducted on the relationship between near-field radiative heat flux and electricity production in TICs due to constraints in characterizing the fluxes independently.

4.2. Thermal resistance of interfaces

Typically, conduction through the spacers has been approximated by Fourier's law. These losses are directly dependent on the surface coverage (SC), thermal conductivity of the spacer material (κ_{spacer}) and length of the spacer (L):

$$Q_{\text{cond}} = h_{\text{cond}} \cdot \Delta T = \frac{SC \cdot \kappa_{\text{spacer}} \cdot \Delta T}{L} \quad (2)$$

To calculate accurately the conduction through the spacers one would require complete knowledge of the height distributions and contact surface areas of the spacers, as well as the deformation of the sample when heat and external forces are applied [70]. Those parameters are not available experimentally and highly depend on the limitations imposed by the fabrication of the spacers. For example, several authors noted a strong disparity in the spacers' heights, which contributed to uncertainty in conduction losses [68,72,104]. The contact area used to determine the surface coverage has also often been approximated, especially in cases of spherical spacers. For example, the contact area of spherical spacers was almost always evaluated by using the cross-sectional area of a cylinder. Only Sabbaghi et al. [99] went beyond this approximation by implementing the Hertz model to estimate the contact area between the polystyrene spheres and emitter/receiver surfaces. Additionally, the value of the thermal conductivity of the

spacer is often taken as tabulated in literature without considering the variation due to temperature changes as discussed previously. Therefore, Equation (2) should be considered an approximation of the conduction losses. Considering interfacial thermal contact resistances between surfaces in a TIC or NF-TPV, illustrated in the thermal circuit on the right side of Fig. 7, represents a more precise approach to evaluating conduction losses through spacers. The total thermal resistance of the vacuum gap R_{gap} can be expressed as:

$$R_{\text{gap}} = R_{\text{e-s}}^{\text{int}} + R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}} + R_{\text{s-r}}^{\text{int}} \quad (3)$$

where $R_{\text{e-s}}^{\text{int}}$ and $R_{\text{s-r}}^{\text{int}}$ are the interfacial thermal contact resistances between the emitter and the spacer and between the spacer and the receiver, respectively. $R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}}$ is the thermal resistance associated with conduction through the spacer; it is dependent on the thermal conductivity of the bulk material which is itself dependent on the temperature of the material:

$$R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}} = \frac{L}{\kappa_{\text{spacer}} A_{\text{spacer}}} \quad (4)$$

In most articles, only $R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}}$ was considered when calculating the conduction losses. This approach is valid for long spacers where $R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}} \gg R_{\text{e-s}}^{\text{int}} + R_{\text{s-r}}^{\text{int}}$. However, when the spacer length decreases, R_{gap} cannot be directly approximated as $R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}}$. This approximation becomes even more inaccurate if the spacer material is characterized by a high thermal conductivity. Therefore, considering the thermal contact resistances at the device's interfaces would result in lower values of the conduction losses since R_{gap} would increase per Equation (3).

If the contribution of the interfacial thermal resistances is considered, the effective conduction losses $Q_{\text{cond,eff}}$ can be expressed as: $Q_{\text{cond,eff}} = \Delta T / R_{\text{gap}}$. This approach has been investigated to various degrees in several articles [22,28,30,69,89,96,104]. In two publications by Ito et al. [69,96], the thermal contact resistance at the top surface of the truncated pyramid spacers, i.e., the thermal contact resistance between the emitter and the spacer, was obtained as a fitting parameter in their model. Ito et al. [69] modeled $R_{\text{e-s}}^{\text{int}}$, $R_{\text{s-r}}^{\text{int}}$ and $R_{\text{spacer}}^{\text{cond}}$ for a single spacer and found that the thermal contact resistances far outweighed the thermal resistance of the spacer structure alone, commenting that thermal contact resistances are vital in suppressing conduction losses through the spacers. Belbachir et al. [28] created an experimental setup for measuring the thermal resistance of the vacuum gap when various pressures ranging from 0.04 MPa to 0.37 MPa were applied. As expected, the thermal resistance of the entire vacuum gap decreased as the applied pressure increased due to the larger contact area formed at the interface between the spacers and the emitter/receiver. When the corresponding conduction losses were calculated using the measured R_{gap} value of $2.4 \text{ K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$, as opposed to Equation (2), which only considers the thermal resistance through the spacer geometry, the magnitude of the conduction losses was cut in half [28], further indicating that Equation (2) overestimates conduction losses. Two years later, the thermal resistance measurements in Ref. [28] were repeated, but the width of the silicon dioxide spacers was varied. The thermal resistance of the entire gap increased as the spacer width decreased, which was expected due to the relationship between thermal resistance and area expressed in Equation (4) [89]. The authors emphasized that experimental measurements were essential to investigate thermal contact resistance, as the validity of a model can be affected by a change of temperature or applied pressure [28,127]. An increase of contact pressure or force applied to the system can lower the interface's thermal resistance by increasing the contact area between the spacer and the surface. In some cases, neglecting thermal contact resistance was justified by the authors. De Sutter et al. [94] ignored it because the SU-8 reflowed and filled any voids during the bonding process, creating a good contact. Finally, Habibzadeh et al. [104] ignored $R_{\text{s-r}}^{\text{int}}$ because the SU-8 spacers were

Fig. 7. Simplified representation (left) and corresponding thermal circuit (right) of a typical emitter/gap/receiver stack. $R_{\text{thermionic}}$ is only present in the case of a thermionic device.

fabricated on the receiver, but R_{e-s}^{int} was included in conduction loss calculations depending on the presence of graphene.

The most straightforward way of increasing interfacial thermal contact resistances has been implementing spherical spacers, since these spacers have a very low contact area [68,87]. Removable spacer films, such as the corrugated films designed by Nicaise et al. [30] and Campbell et al. [31], are also promising and have been more reliable in size and ability to remain fixed during experiments than spheres. In both works, the thermal resistance of the corrugated spacer film was measured for various applied pressures ranging from 1 atm to 5.5 atm. Upon fitting the results to a model that considered surface roughness, Nicaise et al. [30] deduced that approximately one-third of the total thermal resistance could be attributed to the contact resistance between the spacer film and the emitter/receiver surfaces. This result further indicates that contact thermal resistances should not be neglected when evaluating conduction losses, especially in the case of unattached spacers since the lack of attachment results in higher contact resistances. In Ref. [30], the measured thermal resistance was also used to calculate an effective thermal conductivity of the alumina spacer structure of $\sim 5 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, which was lower than SU-8 or other organic materials and on par with insulating aerogels. Later, in Ref. [31], the thermal resistance of a similar corrugated spacer film was further improved by utilizing alumina-hafnia alloys and alumina-hafnia-zirconia nanolaminate films as spacer materials as opposed to pure alumina, and by adding raised protrusions at the intersections of the hexagonal unit cells to increase the contact resistance. The use of multilayered ceramics proved useful in augmenting the overall thermal resistance compared to the pure alumina film because of interlayer interfaces. However, it should be noted that these multilayered films had a thermal resistance that was more sensitive to applied pressure than a pure alumina film.

4.3. Challenges in measuring the gap distance

When characterizing spacers, accurate determination of the vacuum gap distance is essential to extract the contribution of each flux to the total heat transfer that is measured. Several methods of characterizing gap distance have been employed in literature. Some authors relied on reflectometry and curve fitting to approximate the gap distance [69,70,72,74,91,93,96]. This method has proven to be precise, with an error of roughly 10 nm, but it is limited to nonmetallic films due to the opacity of metals. Therefore, reflectometry would be difficult to apply outside of plane-to-plane experiments [99]. Some publications have estimated the gap distance through capacitance measurements between two conductive surfaces [30,31,90,98]. This approach is advantageous because measurements can be taken in-situ, but strong variations in gap distance have been observed depending on the magnitude of the applied force meant to correct bowing [90]. The simplest method has been approximating the gap distance as equivalent to the height of the spacer; this has been employed by the majority of researchers [28,53,68,71,92,94,87–89,97,95,101–103]. In this approach, the height of the spacer has

been measured via direct methods, such as electronic or confocal microscopes. However, the assumption that the length of the spacer equates to the gap distance is valid only if the height distribution of the spacers across the surface is homogeneous, and if both the emitter and receiver's surface are almost perfectly planar. In the case of micro- or nanospheres used as spacers, this method proved to be a poor estimation of the gap size due to the large variation in the spheres' diameters [68,72,87,99]. Furthermore, unlike the reflectometry and capacitance methods, approximating the gap distance as the spacer height completely ignores potential deformation of the spacers under applied forces used to correct any bowing. To rectify this problem, Sabbaghi et al. [99] fit the value obtained for the measured near-field radiative heat flux between two Si plates to a theoretical value obtained by fluctuational electrodynamics. Shi et al. [95,100] relied on height measurements to determine the gap distance in conjunction with Hooke's law, which was implemented to calculate the displacement the SU-8 spacers would undergo due to the applied force on the stack. The gap distance obtained by this method was verified by fitting the measured values to computed values of the radiative heat transfer.

5. Conclusion

Thermionic and thermophotovoltaic energy converters represent an interesting alternative to current thermoelectric converters by enabling potentially higher efficiencies and output power densities. However, to achieve expected performance metrics, both technologies must feature controlled micro- or nano-scale vacuum gaps. Spacers appear to be the most straightforward and scalable design solution for creating nano- and microscale gaps, but these structures introduce a pathway for parasitic conduction losses, unlike other methods such as positioner actuator stages. A wide variety of materials have been tested as candidates for spacers, with the most popular materials being silicon dioxide and organic photoresists. Despite their popularity in the literature, organic photoresists are limited to low-temperature applications and are consequently not feasible for actual devices. Nevertheless, gaps less than 100 nm have only been achieved using SU-8 spacers, indicating that research efforts have yet to achieve NF-TPV devices with very small gaps that are also operational at high temperatures.

For near-field thermophotovoltaics, most experiments achieved relatively low temperature differences between the emitter and receiver and there are only a few experimental devices including a TPV cell. Future publications should focus on exploring a wider range of temperature differences with spacers fabricated from materials more suitable to high-temperature applications, such as ceramics. For thermionics, more devices with spacers have already been fabricated; however, the impact of spacers on the electron flux and the overall efficiency of the system has not been explored. Spacer materials should be chosen according to their thermal and electrical conductivities, as well as their ability to withstand high temperatures and possible compression without breaking. In this regard, ceramics, and especially multilayered

ceramics, present an interesting pathway to reduce greatly the conduction losses between the emitter and the receiver in both technologies. In order to enable devices with higher emitter temperatures, ceramics should be prioritized. Precise engineering of the spacer structures to increase interfacial resistance or conduction length could further reduce the conduction losses.

Finally, attention should be given to the characterization of the gap size and accurate determination of the conduction losses to fully understand the viability of spacers in micro- and nanoscale devices that must withstand multiple thermal cycles. Spacers have been applied only to relatively small areas, but they are scalable to larger areas, which is important in maximizing power output density. As such, understanding their impact on both types of devices should be at the forefront of research efforts, especially to minimize conduction losses while maintaining mechanical robustness.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Nicolas A. Loubet: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Katie Bezdjian:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Esther López:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Alejandro Datas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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